

PERSONAL DEVELOPMENT THROUGH THE DIGITALIZATION OF EDUCATION

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Annotation

The article presents an analysis of the current situation in the field of education in the environment of its digitalization and humanization through the prism of their dialectics. It's shown that digitalization as a complex miracle includes a number of aspects legal, abstract, organizational, methodological and cerebral. Reliance on public traditions, the particular eventuality of preceptors is presented as the base for the humanization of the ultramodern world of digital education. It's concluded that the connection between the frugality and education in the environment of digitalization is a motivation for a formative future of the youthful «digitized» generation, and learning digital chops and capabilities is a factor in youthful people entering the changeable world of professions.

Keywords: digitalization of education, humanization of education, transformation of education.

Аннотация

В статье представлен анализ современной ситуации в сфере образования в условиях его цифровизации и гуманизации через призму их диалектики. Показано, что цифровизация как комплексное чудо включает в себя ряд аспектов правового, абстрактного, организационного, методологического и церебрального. Опора на общественные традиции, особая возможность наставников представлена как основа гуманизации ультрасовременного мира цифрового образования. Сделан вывод о том, что связь бережливости и образования в условиях цифровизации является мотивацией формирующего будущего юношеского «оцифрованного» поколения, а овладение цифровыми навыками и способностями является фактором вхождения молодежи в изменчивый мир профессий.

Ключевые слова: цифровизация образования, гуманизация образования, трансформация образования.

The problem of digitalization of education at the present stage is complex and interdisciplinary in nature, therefore, the main goal should be to study the digitalization of education as a complex scientific, theoretical and practical problem. Philosophical-anthropological and humanitarian approaches are leading to the study of this problem, allowing to identify ideological and ontological issues in connection with the expansion of digitalization in education, accompanied by a transformation of values, a change in the nature of

communications and behavioral models. At present, it is important to be ready and capable of learning, self-education, be able to combine individual components of information, approach problem solving creatively and quickly respond to the requirements and challenges of our time.

The modern world has plunged the education system into a whirlpool of integration processes, giving it a new, extremely intensive, before unknown format in the form of distance, electronic, digital, online, deadline learning, etc. Computers, projectors and gadgets have replaced the notebook, pen, blackboard and chalk. In this regard, the question often arises: is there a need for a Teacher, an Educator, if he ceases to be a source of knowledge? But right away I want to object to myself: the teacher has really ceased to be the only and infallible source of information, but what about the source of knowledge? Is any information obtained on the Internet with the help of information and computer technologies, is knowledge? Does any information carry value, is it important, necessary and reliable? And here the answer is clearly: no!

The modern world, the current generation can no longer be imagined outside the framework of digitalization, but based on a lot of scientific research on this topic, one should pay attention to the fact that digitalization is not just a new phenomenon, it is a multifaceted, complicated phenomenon, especially in the form of digitalization of education. As we have already noted in previous studies on this topic, the aspects of digitalization of education are: the legal aspect (regulatory support), conceptual (there is a need for scientific justification of the following terms: digitalization, e-learning, online learning and distance learning, since they are often used as synonyms), organizational (development and implementation of educational content in the educational process), methodological and psychological (training, training of teachers of both school and vocational education systems, to work in new conditions of transformation of the educational environment using information and computer technologies).

From that moment on, the development of the global economy in a digital format was assumed and the recognition that it was the digital economy that would serve as a powerful impetus for innovation processes, growth and general well-being. Education was also not left without attention, since participation in the digital economy requires certain skills, and therefore, the modern education system should provide students with such training systems that would be aimed at identifying the demand for general and specialized digital skills through continuous professional education. Requirements for vocational education have also changed as the requirements for potential workers in the digital economy have changed.

Inspired by the new idea, scientists massively turned to research on the digitalization of the economy and education. At the same time, there are scientists who, without denying the achievements of modern science and technology, current trends in society, are puzzled by the problem of excessive enthusiasm for technologization of education. In the recent past, we have already encountered the interpretation of education as a service, since the concept of “non-budgetary form of education”, “paid educational services”, etc. has appeared. The authors raise the question of the relationship between digitalization and humanization of education, the role of cognitive-creative interaction between students and teachers. E. A. Yamburg wrote that the pedagogical theory of the 21st century is in a long search for forms of education, since the new young generation declares new aspirations and tasks, but at the same time, it is this generation that needs to make up for the “globally lost” worldview culture. preservation of the fundamental foundations in education, its national traditions.

An example is scientific mentoring in the system of higher education, when from the first year the most capable and interested students are engaged in research activities with a specific teacher-scientist in various forms. The most common types of such activities are writing scientific articles in collaboration with a teacher or under his guidance, participation in the work of scientific and practical conferences, round tables, disputes, scientific competitions, etc. Traditionally, scientific circles are created at the departments of universities, the purpose of which also is the development of students' research skills, in-depth study of scientific problems and the involvement of other students in the world of student science.

Analyzing many domestic and foreign scientific publications on digitalization, it can be assumed that the authors tend to directly link education with the economy, and sometimes perceive education exclusively for the economy. Colleagues from abroad also turn to the problems of digitalization of education, they are also sure that digital technologies are an integral part of the modern educational process. Foreign and domestic authors say that the digitalization of education has radically changed the relationship between a teacher and a student.

This is due to the fact that the modern student has free access to various sources of information, unlike the classical form of education, and therefore the

teaching methodology for such curious minds must develop rapidly, become more interactive and attractive thanks to digital technologies. Digitalization does not imply a complete rejection of the human factor in education, it is about a new place and quality of teachers in the digital society and the field of education in general. The teacher will become not so much a translator of knowledge as a mentor and facilitator, whose task is to help students adapt and apply the acquired knowledge in practice.

As before, both in our country and abroad, there is a great fear of change, loss of one's own "I", there is no orientation towards stability and strategic vision. Thus, research on the topic of digitalization of education suggests that the "digital world" has come into its own, this is an objective process, and no matter how we treat it, it has taken a certain place in all spheres of public life and in education, including number. Many universities have developed targeted programs for the digitalization of education, introduced programs for the electronic information and educational environment, in which teachers and students have been successfully working for several years. This stimulates continuous professional development, development of e-learning skills.

The asynchronous organization of the educational process implies the downloading and transfer of educational content within the framework of the educational program in a particular area of study, the independent mastering of the presented material by the student during the semester and the provision of reports to the teacher in electronic form according to an individual training schedule (according to the schedule of the educational process).

Organization of educational activities in the digital environment, adaptation to consumer requirements, correction of the content of education in accordance with changes in economic activity, creativity of teachers, their competence in the field of ICT use, readiness and ability to learn should become a motive for changing society. Such improvement of the education system will provide the digital economy with competent personnel.

Education as a whole should contribute to the development of the individual and society without prejudice to the axiological component of the education process. And even this short path that we have traveled together with our students allows us to say that no technologization can interfere with fruitful communication with students, scientific creative research. Also, when we raise the question: digitalization or humanization, then we should probably answer:

digitalization and humanization, since digitalization is an objective component of our world in the first decades of the 21st century, but humanization is a subjective factor that depends only on the subject of pedagogical activity, namely from the Teacher, the Educator

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